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CONSERVING WATER THROUGH SCIENCE AND TRADITION (A CASE STUDY FOR SOLAPUR)

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ABSTRACT

Indian tourism is essentially driven by temple cities. Among these various ancient temple towns & cities, Solapur is not only important but also unique. The project of 'Suvarna Solapur' is recent launched which will attract maximum numbers of tourists in the coming year. According to the Department of Tourism, in 2015 solapur temple attracts the maximum number of tourists' visiting South India a phenomenal 2.5 crore people. This number is bound to increase in the future threatening the fragile eco-system. Hence there is a need to develop a holistic & sustainable model for a green tourism as well as pilgrimage experience. The mission for green solapur has a three dimensional approach:

1. Discovering Linkages
2. Reviving Relations
3. Creating Nodes and Networks

First dimension is to revive our cultural and ecological linkages. And use them for the social economic development of our people. Second dimension is the reviving of the relations at social, organizational and individual level and coordinate them positively. Third dimension is creation of nodes and networks whose purpose range from the solid waste management to greening of the island to preserving of the cultural heritage of the island.

The project has identified eleven key areas for concentrated and holistic development. This involves the following points:

1. Conserving and popularizing archeology and cultural.
2. Conserving and creating awareness about marine bio-diversity
3. Solid waste management
4. Renewable energy
5. Rain water harvesting
6. Participatory eco-tourism with high lighting of local traditions
7. Sewage treatment
8. Social engineering
9. Creation of new merchandise and livelihood opportunities
10. Green transport
11. Landscaping and beautification.

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